

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Phenomenological Analysis of Teachers' Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Teaching Science

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ABSTRACT

Teachers' knowledge of science concepts and skills, and how these can be transferred to and learned by the pupils through pedagogical efforts is fundamental in teaching science. This knowledge is defined by Shulman (1986) as Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) which is required for teachers to exemplify. Carried out through phenomenological analysis, this study investigated teachers' PCK in teaching science. Data were collected from the five public elementary school teachers through individual and group interviews. Findings show that teachers were oriented to subject-matter goals which emphasize on transmitting curricular objectives. Teachers were aware of the spiral progression of the science concepts in the curriculum, and they need to be knowledgeable of the specific content objectives and the increasing level of difficulty from one grade level to another in spiral progression. Teachers have a clear understanding of a) the importance of the pupils' prior knowledge, b) addressing pupils' misconception and difficulties in learning science; and c) the need to be mindful of these specific topics, misconceptions and difficulties. Further, teachers tended to use traditional assessment and used teacher-centered instructions. Finally, findings show that teachers need to enhance their knowledge of the instructional approaches in teaching science. Implications and recommendations were discussed in the study.

Key words: *Pedagogical content knowledge, Knowledge of Science Curriculum*

INTRODUCTION

It is the ultimate goal of science education to develop scientific literacy among learners that will prepare them to be informed and participative citizens who are able to make judgments and decisions regarding applications of scientific knowledge that may have social, health, or environmental impacts (K-12 Science Curriculum, 2013). In attaining this goal, science teaching shall provide learners with a repertoire of competencies important in the world of work and in a knowledge-based society. For this reason, teachers play an important role in attaining this educational goal.

The educational reform and current goals are envisioned to recast the Philippine educational system more qualitatively than structurally, resulting in the emergence of new roles for teachers, particularly science teachers (UNESCO, 2013). The new roles of the science teachers, according to UNESCO require them to become updated and competent, socially and environmentally-oriented, knowledgeable and skillful, ingenious and resourceful lesson planners and organizer, articulate and efficient instructors, and perceptive evaluators.

In the Department of Education (DepEd), as early as kindergarten, simple science concepts such as healthful habits and curiosity about self and

environment were integrated in the learning areas. Science is formally introduced as one of the core learning areas in elementary and secondary during grade three with different concepts and skills in Life Sciences, Physics, Chemistry, and Earth Sciences (Science Curriculum, 2013). For this reason, teachers should possess sufficient knowledge of science concepts and skills and how these can be transferred to and learned by the pupils through pedagogical efforts. This knowledge is defined by Shulman (1986) as Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) which is required for teachers to exemplify. Teachers' PCK may include their knowledge of the curriculum, how students learn science, instructional approaches and strategies, and assessment of learning, (Magnusson et al., 1999). Further, teachers' application of mastery of content knowledge and its application across learning areas; and facilitating learning using appropriate and innovative teaching strategies and classroom management practices are two of the important roles and duties teachers are to perform (RPMS Manual, 2018). With this, teachers should have specialized training in teaching science to demonstrate their content and pedagogic knowledge.

Notably, in the DepEd, especially in the elementary, out-of-field teaching is a phenomenon. Science classes are handled by teachers who do not have specialized training in teaching science. For example, in the district of Kalilangan East, Division of Bukidnon, among the 187 elementary teachers, only six (6) teachers specialized science teaching in their baccalaureate (School Report Card, 2017). In this vein, studies on PCK show that science teachers who have specialized training in teaching science during their pre-service and in-service have adequate PCK. Their training in college or university has equipped them sufficient PCK they could demonstrate during their in-service teaching (Can, Erokten, and Bahtiyar, 2012; Nuangchalerm, 2012; Nordin and Ariffin, 2016).

In addition, reports of school-based and district trainings show that schools prioritized trainings on gender and development (GAD), school-based management (SBM), Results-based Performance and Management System (RPMS) and other activities related to school management (School Report Card, 2017). Specialized training on teaching science is supposed to equip teachers with pedagogic and content knowledge in teaching science. Teachers'

PCK influences student achievement in elementary science (Lange, Kleickmann, and Möller, 2012). For this reason, teachers play an important role on students' academic achievement, attitudes, attributes, and beliefs, Nuangchalerm (2012).

With cited situation, it is deemed necessary to investigate elementary teachers' PCK to establish a clear representation of the conditions of teacher's PCK. This could be made as bases for policy planning and implementation of science curriculum to sustain teachers' PCK and to address the challenges in science teaching. This study assumed that the elementary school teachers have orientations in teaching science considering knowledge of science curriculum; knowledge of students' understanding of science; knowledge of instructional strategy, and knowledge of assessment of scientific literacy. Thus, Magnusson et al. 1999) model of PCK was used to investigate teachers PCK in teaching science.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK)

PCK is a central component of the teachers' practical knowledge and is based on both subject matter knowledge and pedagogical knowledge (Van Driel et al., 2001; Van Driel, De Jong, & Verloop, 2002). Teaching experience also influences the development of PCK (Clermont, Borko, & Krajcik, 1994). Shulman (1986, 1987) expressed the need for a theoretical formulation to identify the different components of teachers' teaching capabilities, as well as the conditions for developing them. He classified teachers' knowledge into content knowledge (subject matter knowledge), pedagogical knowledge, and pedagogical content knowledge. Pedagogical content knowledge was introduced as a concept that represents the kind of knowledge that teachers' subject matter knowledge and PCK is critical for our success in science teacher education' (Abell, 2007).

Shulman (1986, 1987) described PCK as a unique form of knowledge for teaching which is based on subject matter knowledge, knowledge of potential student learning difficulties, and students' prior knowledge of specific concepts, as well as the most

effective models, analogies, illustrations, explanations, and investigations to make the concept understandable for students. Shulman (1986) explained that PCK conceptualizes 'the ways of representing and formulating subject that makes it comprehensible to others. In 1987, Shulman rephrased his definition of PCK as a 'special amalgam of content and pedagogy that is uniquely the province of teachers, their own special form of professional understanding'. In his understanding, teachers use both their content knowledge and their pedagogical knowledge in a blended way to promote student learning.

Magnusson et al. (1999) proposed a PCK model, which has been widely used to understand science teaching. After Schulman (1987) and later Grossman (1990), they posited that in order to teach certain content, several types of knowledge, including subject matter knowledge, are transformed into the PCK suitable for teaching.

Anchored upon the work of Grossman (1990) and Tamir (1988), Magnusson et al. (1999) conceptualize PCK for science teaching as consisting of five components: 1) orientations toward science teaching, 2) knowledge and beliefs about science curriculum, 3) knowledge and beliefs about students' understanding of specific science topics, 4) knowledge and beliefs about assessment in science, and 5) knowledge and beliefs about instructional strategies for teaching science.

Orientations toward Teaching Science. This component of PCK refers to teachers' knowledge and beliefs about the purposes and goals for teaching science at a particular grade level. Grossman designated this component as consisting of knowledge of the purposes for teaching a subject at a particular grade level or the "overarching conceptions" of teaching a particular subject. Research in science education has referred to this component as "orientations toward science teaching and learning," (Anderson & Smith, 1987), which we prefer to Grossman's term. An orientation represents a general way of viewing or conceptualizing science teaching. The significance of this component is that these knowledge and beliefs serve as a "conceptual map" that guides instructional decisions about issues such as daily objectives, the content of student assignments, the use of textbooks and other curricular

materials, and the evaluation of student learning (Borko & Putnam, 1996).

Beliefs about goals of science teaching are not limited with subject matter goals as Magnusson et al. (1999) claimed. Thus, teachers' beliefs are categorized in this study as affective domain goals, general schooling goals and subject matter goals after participants' central goals and peripheral goals are determined. Schooling goals consider students' preparation to university and life while affective goals are based on attitude towards science, self-confidence, and curiosity. On the other hand, subject matter goals focus on transmitting content knowledge (Friedrichsen & Dana, 2005).

Knowledge of Science Curriculum. This component of PCK consists of two categories: mandated goals and objectives, and specific curricular programs and materials. Shulman and colleagues originally considered curricular knowledge to be a separate domain of the knowledge base for teaching (Wilson, Shulman, & Richert, 1988). Following the lead of Grossman (1990), Magnusson (1999) included it as part of PCK because it represents knowledge that distinguishes the content specialist from the pedagogue—a feature of PCK.

The knowledge of goals and objectives as category of the curricular knowledge component of PCK includes teachers' knowledge of the goals and objectives for students in the subject(s) they are teaching, as well as the articulation of those guidelines across topics addressed during the school year. It also includes the knowledge teachers have about the vertical curriculum in their subject(s); that is, what students have learned in previous years and what they are expected to learn in later years. (Grossman, 1990). On the other hand, knowledge of specific curricular program consists of knowledge of the programs and materials that are relevant to teaching a particular domain of science and specific topics within that domain.

Knowledge of Students' Understanding of Science. This third component of PCK refers to the knowledge teachers must have about students in order to help them develop specific scientific knowledge. It includes two categories of knowledge: requirements for learning specific science concepts, and areas of science that students find difficult.

Knowledge of requirements for learning as one category of teachers' knowledge on students' understanding in science consists of teachers' knowledge and beliefs about prerequisite knowledge for learning specific scientific knowledge, as well as their understanding of variations in students' approaches to learning as they relate to the development of knowledge within specific topic areas. Teacher knowledge of prerequisite knowledge required for students to learn specific concepts includes knowledge of the abilities and skills that students might need. On the other hand, knowledge of areas of student difficulty refers to teachers' knowledge of the science concepts or topics that students find difficult to learn. There are several reasons why students find learning difficult in science, and teachers should be knowledgeable about each type of difficulty (Magnusson et al., 1999).

Knowledge of Assessment in Science. Magnusson et al. (1999) conceptualized this component of PCK, which was originally proposed by Tamir (1988), as consisting of two categories: knowledge of the dimensions of science learning that are important to assess, and knowledge of the methods by which that learning can be assessed. Knowledge of dimensions of science learning to assess refers to teachers' knowledge of the aspects of students' learning that are important to assess within a particular unit of study. In keeping with a major goal of school science, which is to produce a scientifically literate citizenry (Hurd, 1989), the dimensions upon which teacher knowledge in this category is based are those of scientific literacy. On the other hand, knowledge of methods of assessment refers to teachers' knowledge of the ways that might be employed to assess the specific aspects of student learning that are important to a particular unit of study. There are a number of methods of assessment, some of which are more appropriate for assessing some aspects of student learning than others (Magnusson et al., 1999).

Knowledge of Instructional Strategies. Teachers' knowledge of the instructional strategies component of PCK is comprised of two categories: knowledge of subject-specific strategies, and knowledge of topic-specific strategies. Strategies in these categories differ with respect to their scope. Subject-specific strategies are broadly applicable; they are specific to teaching science as opposed to other subjects. Topic-specific strategies are much narrower in scope; they

apply to teaching particular topics within a domain of science. Knowledge of subject-specific strategies represents general approaches to or overall schemes for enacting science instruction. Teachers' knowledge of subject-specific strategies is related to the "orientations to teaching science" component of PCK in that there are general approaches to science instruction that are consistent with the goals of particular orientations. Knowledge of topic-specific strategies, on the other hand, refers to teachers' knowledge of specific strategies that are useful for helping students comprehend specific science concepts (Magnusson et al., 1999).

Carried out through Transcendental Phenomenological Analysis (Moustakas, 1994), and anchored to the concept of Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Science Teaching (Magnusson et al., 1999), this study investigated teachers' pedagogical content knowledge in teaching science by describing their lived-experiences.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study investigated the pedagogical content knowledge in teaching science of public elementary school teachers in the Schools Division of Bukidon for the school year 2018-2019. Specifically, this study aimed to answer:

1. What is the Pedagogical Content Knowledge of public elementary school teachers in teaching science considering the following:
 - 1.1 Orientation of science teaching;
 - 1.2 Knowledge of science curriculum;
 - 1.3 Knowledge of pupils' understanding of science;
 - 1.4 Knowledge of instructional strategy, and
 - 1.5 Knowledge of assessment of scientific literacy?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A qualitative phenomenological research design was carried out to investigate teachers' PCK in teaching science, more specifically of Moustakas's (1994) descriptive phenomenological approach which focuses less on the interpretations of the researcher and more on a description of the experiences of participants. In addition, Moustakas

Table 1. Profile of the Research Participants

Participant	District	Years in service	Bachelor degree and Specialization	Training attended related to Science Teaching in the last three years
Teacher 1	Kalilangan East	9	Elementary Education, Gen. Ed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical Content in teaching Science,
Teacher 2	Kalilangan West	4	Elementary Education, Gen. Ed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K-12 Program Basic Education Program
Teacher 3	Kalilangan East	5	Elementary Education, English	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K-12 Program Basic Education Program
Teacher 4	Pangantucan South	15	Elementary Education, Filipino	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K-12 Program Basic Education Program
Teacher 5	Pangantucan North	10	Elementary Education, Aral. Pan.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K-12 Program Basic Education Program

focuses on one of Husserl's concepts, epoche or bracketing, in which investigators set aside their experiences, as much as possible, to take a fresh perspective toward the phenomenon under examination.

Phenomenological research is a design of inquiry coming from philosophy and psychology in which the researcher describes the lived experiences of individuals about a phenomenon as described by participants. This description culminates in the essence of the experiences for several individuals who have all experienced the phenomenon. This design has strong philosophical underpinnings and typically involves conducting interviews (Giorgi, 2009; Moustakas, 1994). The present study ascertained PCK of public school teachers by investigating their lived experiences in teaching science.

Participants of the study were the 5 public elementary school teachers from the different schools' districts in the division of Bukidnon for the school year 2018-2019. Creswell (2013) posited that sample size depends on the qualitative design being used. From his review of many qualitative research studies, sample size for phenomenology typically range from three to ten.

Samples were purposively identified to participate in the study. The idea behind qualitative research purposeful selection of participants or sites will best help the researcher understand the problem

and the research question (Creswell, 2014). Purposive sampling seeks information-rich cases, which are suited in in-depth studies (Creswell, 2012).

Sampling criteria involved in this study anchored on the notions of Miles and Huberman (1994) which suggest that the identification of participants and site in a qualitative research might include four aspects: a) the setting-where the research will take place, b) the actors-who will be observed or interviewed, c) the events-what the actors will be observed or interviewed doing, and d) the process-the evolving nature of events undertaken by the actors within the setting. Thus, the samples involved in this study were the 5 public elementary school grade six science teachers (actors) from the different school's districts in the division of Bukidnon (setting). The samples were at least in the service teaching science with a very satisfactory performance rating for the last three years (events). And finally, they were not science major in their teacher preparation (process). Table 1 shows profile of the teachers.

DATA COLLECTION

This study used both qualitative interviews involving face-to-face interviews with participants, and focus group. Interviewing in qualitative research is increasingly being seen as a moral inquiry (Kvale, 2007). It could equally be seen as such for quantitative and mixed methods research. As such, Creswell (2012) stated that interviewers need to consider how the interview will improve the human

situation as well as enhance scientific knowledge, how a sensitive interview interaction may be stressful for the participants, whether participants have a say in how their statements are interpreted, how critically the interviewees might be questioned, and what the consequences of the interview for the interviewees and the groups to which they belong might be.

With the cited notions, interview protocol was structured anchored to literature on PCK in science teaching (Magnuson et al., 1999) to collect in-depth data from the participants. To establish validity of the data collection tool, the interview protocol was evaluated by experts according to its content validity.

Ethical Consideration

Considering research ethics, preliminary requirements such as permission, informed consent were secured. The researchers sought a letter of permission indicating its purpose and significance from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent for the conduct of the study.

The two-part informed consents from the participants were secured. Information Sheet (Part I) includes the title of the research, author's names and designation, a brief introduction, aims, participant selection and voluntary participation to the study. It was clearly indicated that they can choose to participate or not; and that the data from their participation would be kept with utmost confidentiality. Certificate of Consent (Part II) indicates the provisions to agree or disagree in the data gathering procedures. Participants affixed their signature for the agreement to the provisions.

DATA ANALYSIS

Phenomenological data analysis steps by Moustakas (1994) were used in this study because it has systematic steps in the data analysis procedure and guidelines for assembling the textural and structural descriptions. The major procedural steps in the process were as follows. Building on the data from the research questions, the researchers went through the data from interview transcriptions and highlighted "significant statements," sentences, or quotes that provide an understanding of how the participants experienced the phenomenon. Moustakas (1994) called this step horizontalization.

Next, the researchers developed clusters of meaning from these significant statements into themes. These significant statements and themes will be used to write a description of what the participants experienced (textural description). The researchers also wrote a description of the context or setting that influenced how the participants experienced the phenomenon. Moustakas (1994) called this imaginative variation or structural description.

From the structural and textural descriptions, the researchers then wrote a composite description that presents the "essence" of the phenomenon, called the essential, invariant structure (or essence). Primarily this passage focuses on the common experiences of the participants (Creswell, 2006). Finally, to establish reliability, the analysis of the data was evaluated by experts to validate that the themes, the description, and the analysis capture the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Teachers' Pedagogical Content Knowledge in Teaching Science

The five components of PCK (Magnusson et al., 1991) which are orientation towards science, knowledge of curriculum, knowledge of students' understandings, knowledge of assessments and knowledge of instructional strategies were used to understand teachers' PCK in teaching science.

Teachers' Orientation towards Science

Teachers' beliefs about the goals of science teaching were investigated to understand their orientation towards science since beliefs shapes teachers' decision and practice. Teachers (n=4) emphasized the importance of the development of scientific literacy in preparing the pupils as twenty-first century learners. They recognized the role of science of making pupils lifelong learners equipped with scientific skills and awareness of their environment. Teachers (n=3) believed that the goal of science teaching is to equip pupils with scientific knowledge and skills that could be applied in their daily life. The knowledge and skills acquired by the pupils are important in preparing them for further education.

Teachers' orientations are multi-dimensional and complex, so it is difficult to change teachers' orientations according to Luft and Roehring (2007). It can be gleaned from the data that teachers' orientation of the goals of science teaching is to make pupils scientifically literate and environmentally aware life-long learners. This orientation corresponds to subject matter goals according to Friedrichsen and Dana (2005). With this kind of orientation, teachers tend to give emphasis on transmitting curricular objectives. They are teacher-centered in the teaching and learning process and oriented on lecture/discussion, teacher demonstration, and academic rigor.

On the other hand, teachers' orientation to schooling goals which consider pupils' preparation to high school and life is also evident from the data. It is notable, however, that teachers' orientation on affective goals was not mentioned by the participants. Affective goals are based on attitude towards science, self-confidence, and curiosity (Friedrichsen and Dana, 2005). The findings can be gleaned from the following statements of the participants.

"Science teaching is preparing the twenty-first century pupils to be scientifically skilled learners. The goal of science teaching is for them (learners) to be scientifically skilled, and to aware them to apply science in real life situation." (T1)

"Science teaching is the) pillar for discovery in preparation for high school." (T4)

Teachers' Knowledge of Science Curriculum

In this study, teachers' knowledge of the science curriculum includes knowledge of goals and objectives, and knowledge of materials. The knowledge of goals and objectives includes teachers' knowledge of the goals and objectives for students in the science, as well as the articulation of those guidelines across topics addressed during the school year. It also includes the knowledge teachers have about the vertical curriculum in science. On the other hand, knowledge of specific curricular program consists of knowledge of the programs and materials

that are relevant to teaching a particular domain of science and specific topics within that domain.

Knowledge of Goals and Objectives. Teachers (n=5) can recognize the topic in the first quarter which is the "Matter". But, when asked why this topic is taught and included in science curriculum, teachers (n=3) could not cite reason. They were also uncertain if there were any topics in the present grade level that were related to "matter". Notably, teachers (n=2) emphasized the application and usefulness in daily life of skills that can be learned from the learning competencies on "matter". They also acknowledged that the concept is taught throughout elementary grade levels. Teachers were aware of the spiral progression of the domains of science teaching, but as to the details and level of progression, they were not well acquainted with it.

From the data, it can be gleaned that teachers have the knowledge of the thematic topics and the sequences of domains; and they were aware that there is knowledge that pupils had to learn which would serve as prior knowledge to the present concepts. Further, they were familiar of what their pupils will be learning in their later grade levels. They were aware of the vertical curriculum (Clark, 2000; Magnusson et al. 1999), and the horizontal curriculum (Brown, 1990; Kindfield, 1994; Lewis et al., 2000) of science teaching. They, however, have limitations of the knowledge of objectives (Aydemir, 2014) of the specific topic. They were also dependent to the curriculum materials (Cochran et al., 1993) such as curriculum guides and teaching guides they have retrieved from the LRMSD portal of the DepEd. However, they lack the knowledge of the spiral progression of these concepts in the elementary and secondary. Spiral progression is presentation of science concepts and skills with increasing levels of complexity from one grade level to another in spiral progression, thus paving the way to a deeper understanding of core concepts (K-12 Science Curriculum, 2013). This can be noted in the reports of the participants.

"Children are taught on how to separate mixture such as sieving, sifting, and winnowing and others. These are important skills that are experienced daily." (T4)

"From the kindergarten, they (pupils) are learning simple things on matter." (T5)

"The simple concept (of "matter") is taught in the lower level. (It is) maybe (taught) in the grade IV." (T1)

Knowledge of Materials. Teachers (n=5) used activity sheets, modules, and videos downloaded from the internet as learning resources in teaching science. They (n=3) also used real objects because these materials would allow pupils to concretize the concept since they can manipulate and visualize the materials. One of them also expressed that he used textbooks from the lower grades as these contain concepts that are prior to their learning. Teachers (n=2) also used books from the private school and downloaded learning materials from the DepEd learning resources website because as of this writing, there is no available textbook for science six.

"I used downloaded data, (and) videos from the internet. I also used textbooks from lower grades." (T4)

"They understand easily because they can concretize the concept through the use of real object. ... I also use (learning resources from) internet. There are no available books for pupils." (T2)

Knowledge of Students' Understanding of Science

Knowledge of requirements for learning and knowledge of students' difficulties are investigated to understand teachers' PCK of students' understanding of science. With regards to the former, teachers recognized the importance of establishing the prior knowledge in the concept to be learned. However, when asked what prior knowledge pupils should have to understand first before teaching "matter", only two teachers able to cite these topics. On the other hand, teachers (n=3) could not cite specific topics or lessons that pupils find difficulty in understanding. Two teachers, however, emphasized the concepts of "separating mixture", and "gaseous elements" as the difficult concepts for the pupils to learn. Pupils have difficulty in understanding that when mixed together, materials may not form new ones thus these materials

may be recovered using different separation techniques.

Teachers (n=4) could not cite specific topics on "matter" which pupils have misconception. But, they can explain why misconception among pupils happens. Pupils' lack or low mastery of the concept in their early grades leads to misconception. Notably, only one teacher had express pupils' misconception regarding properties of gaseous element. Further, teachers, when asked how they identify pupils' misconception, different responses such as through the evaluation (n=3), during classroom instruction specifically during discussion and activities (n=2) were expressed.

The data implied that teachers' have a clear understanding of the importance of the pupils' prior knowledge as requirement for successful learning. They also have the knowledge of pupils' misconception and difficulties in learning science but they were unmindful of these specific misconceptions and difficulties. Teachers' assessing pupils' misconception and difficulty through evaluating pupils' understanding is the best way according to Sen (2014). However, Park and Oliver (2008) claimed that it is not always possible to assess students. Teachers should have the knowledge of pupils' common misconception and difficulties. These notions had been practiced by the teachers in the present study.

"...during the teaching and learning process. I can really spot that pupils have misconception. I have to pause for a while because they are having difficulty in understanding. Their answers in their activity are wrong. (During) evaluation. Their participation is poor because they are having misconception. Sometimes, there is a total silence. That silence might be an indicator of confusion or misconception." (T1)

Knowledge of Assessment

Teachers' knowledge of assessment was another component of PCK revealed in this study. Knowledge of assessment includes two sub-domains in terms of knowledge of dimensions of science learning to

assess and knowledge of methods of assessment (Magnusson et al., 1999).

Knowledge of Dimensions of Science Learning to Assess. Teachers have different orientations in assessing pupils learning in science. Some (n=3) preferred to assess only pupils' conceptual understanding. While other teachers (n=2) assessed pupils' demonstration and application of the knowledge. In the K-12 Curriculum (2013) demonstration of scientific inquiry skills, understanding and application of scientific knowledge, and development and demonstrations of scientific attitude and values are the dimension of learning to be assessed. However, in this study, it was found that teachers focused on assessing students' conceptual understanding and application of scientific knowledge, and demonstration of skills. Teachers focused less on assessing the affective domain of teaching science which is demonstration of scientific attitude and values. This result is similar to previous research (Sen, 2014; Lankford, 2010; Tekkaya & Kılıç, 2012). Although teachers were subject matter goal oriented which aim to transmit curricular objectives, they also assessed other dimensions of scientific knowledge and skills. Teacher expressed during the interview:

"I assessed if students can apply the (concept of the) lesson. If they could demonstrate... for example... what activity would show the change of solid to liquid. They would show it by melting the ice." (T2)

Knowledge of Methods of Assessment. Teachers' knowledge of methods of assessment refers to how to and when to assess pupils' learning. Teachers (n=4) used traditional way of assessing pupils' learning through paper-pencil test, activity, and worksheet. Only one teacher emphasized pupil demonstration of the skills using experiment.

Findings show that teachers tended to use traditional assessment. This finding is similar with the study of Canbazoglu et al., 2010; Graf et al., 2011; Yarden & Cohen, 2009). Teachers' orientation again could be related with their use of assessment technique because their orientation towards science is teacher-centered as mentioned before. On the other hand, alternative assessment techniques such as

performance assessment and portfolio are student-centered assessment techniques (Sen, 2014). Therefore, as it is expected science teachers preferred to use traditional assessment techniques which are consistent with their orientation.

Another sub-dimension of teachers' knowledge of assessment is related to the time of assessment. Teachers (n=3) used both summative and formative assessment after the end of the lesson covering all the competencies the pupils had learned. On the other hand, two teachers used questioning to elicit pupils' understanding of the concept at the beginning of the lesson, and at the end of the lesson. Generally, all of the teachers used summative assessment at the end of the lesson.

Time of assessment includes both formative assessment (assessment for learning) and summative assessment (assessment of learning) as suggested by Earle (2014). In the present study, it was found that teachers used both formative and summative assessment. It is expected, according to Sen, (2014) that science teachers should always assess their students' understandings to help their needs, to elicit their misconceptions, to provoke them towards further learning and to recall their prior knowledge. These findings can be gleaned from the responses of the teachers.

"I evaluate pupils' performance through paper-pen test, worksheet..." (T3)

"I assess after the end of the lesson." (T4)

Knowledge of Instructional Strategies

Knowledge of instructional strategies included two sub-dimensions which are subject specific strategies and topic specific strategies. Teachers (n=3) are oriented to teacher-centered strategies such as the use of teacher demonstration, lecture, and question and answer. They were opted to use these strategies because their pupils have difficulty in learning science concepts and they have to take charge in teaching-learning process.

Teachers' knowledge of topic specific strategies included two sub-dimensions which are knowledge of

representation and knowledge of activities. Teachers (n=5) used real objects and models, visuals, videos, drawings, and powerpoint presentation to illustrate the concepts in teaching science. Teachers (n=3) demonstrate the science concept through demonstrations of the process. For example, they would teach the concept of evaporation, solidification, liquefying, sublimation and other concepts by doing simple demonstration like boiling water, and melting ice.

Teachers' knowledge of topic specific strategies included two sub-dimensions which are knowledge of representation and knowledge of activities. With regards to teachers' knowledge of representation, teachers (n=5) used real objects and models, visuals, videos, drawings, and powerpoint presentation to illustrate the concepts in teaching science. Teachers (n=3) demonstrate the science concept through demonstrations of the process. For example, they would teach the concept of evaporation, solidification, liquefying, sublimation and other concepts by doing simple demonstration like boiling water, and melting ice.

Finally, with regards to knowledge of activities, teachers used demonstrations, experiments, and hands-on activities. For example, teachers let the pupils demonstrate by crumpling, tearing, and burning paper to teach the concept of physical and chemical change. All of them expressed that they used experiments although they do not have science laboratory in the school. They improvised materials that are available.

"... we do experimentation. In the absence of science laboratory, we use what are available and improvise these materials. There are many materials in the kitchen that can be used." (T3)

The last component of the PCK is the knowledge of instructional strategies which comprises of subject specific strategies, and topic specific strategies. It can be gleaned from the data that participants used teacher-centered instructions which are lecture, discussion, and teacher demonstration. In the interview, they did not mention that they use student-centered or constructivist approaches. Findings of this study about knowledge of instructional strategies are consistent with the research of Brown et al. (2013);

and Sen (2014). The reason teachers might not be using student-centered instructions could be related with their orientations. Because of their focus is on transmitting curricular objectives, they preferred to use instructional strategies that are consistent with their orientation at most. That is direct instruction.

Teachers used representations and some activities in teaching science concepts as topic specific instructional strategies. One of the teachers used model to represent "matter". The use of model to teach science concepts are common in literature (Clark, 2000; Mickle, 1990). Teachers also used visuals and drawings as illustrations to visualize abstract cell division topics. This conforms to the findings of Cho et al., (1985). Similarly, teachers used examples to link abstract ideas and concrete things (Hume & Berry, 2011). It can be noted with the following statements of the participants.

"Aside from the illustration, I use real object and demonstration. Like for example, in our classroom we would boil water to show the concept of evaporation, we would melt an ice to show the concept of melting. ... especially when I teach the concept of homogenous and heterogeneous properties of matter." (T1)

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

Analysis of the data collected through individual and group interviews from the five participants revealed that they were oriented on subject-matter goal which emphasizes on transmitting curricular objectives. Teachers were aware of the spiral progression of science concepts in the curriculum, but they have limited knowledge of the specific content objectives and the increasing level of difficulty from one grade level to another in spiral progression. They have a clear understanding of the importance of the pupils' prior knowledge as requirement for successful learning, misconception and difficulties in learning science but they were unmindful of these specific topics, misconceptions and difficulties. Further, teachers tended to use traditional assessment and used teacher-centered instructions. Finally, data shows that they have limited knowledge of instructional approaches in teaching science.

IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results have important implications for science teachers, researchers and curriculum developers about teachers' PCK in teaching science. This study revealed that teachers were oriented on subject-matter goals. With this kind of orientation, teachers tend to give emphasis on transmitting curricular objectives. They tend to be teacher-centered in the teaching and learning process and oriented on lecture/discussion, teacher demonstration, and academic rigor.

With these findings, it is recommended for the teachers to develop their PCK orientations not only on the subject matter goals and schooling goals but also with the affective goals of teaching science. According to Friedrichsen & Dana (2005) affective goals are based on attitude towards science, self-confidence, and curiosity. Teachers, therefore, should also orient themselves on how they can develop pupils' scientific attitudes and values.

With regards to knowledge of curriculum, teachers were aware of the concept of spiral progression of science curriculum: vertical curriculum (Clark, 2000; Magnusson et al. 1999), and the horizontal curriculum (Brown, 1990; Kindfield, 1994; Lewis et al., 2000). They, however, have limited knowledge of the specific content objectives (Aydemir, 2014) and the level of progression of these concepts. It is recommended that teachers should not only have sufficient knowledge of the science curriculum spiral progression, they should know with the specific topic objectives and the level of difficulty of the scientific concepts across all grade levels.

With regard to knowledge of pupils' understanding science, teachers' have a clear understanding of the importance of the pupils' prior knowledge as requirement for successful learning, misconception and difficulties in learning science but they were unmindful of these topic specific misconceptions and difficulties. It is recommended that teachers should be knowledgeable with the pedagogy and the content of teaching specific science skills. They must understand psychological principles on how their pupils learn.

Teachers focus to assess students' conceptual understanding and application of scientific

knowledge, and demonstration of skills. Teachers tended to use traditional assessment. Teachers assessed pupil's science learning through formative assessment (assessment for learning) and summative assessment (assessment of learning), (Earle, 2014). Along with assessing pupils' scientific inquiry skills, and scientific knowledge; it is recommended that teachers should also assess pupils' scientific attitudes and values. They may also use other assessment techniques such as performance-based and portfolio-based.

Matrix 1. Area and emphasis of teachers' professional development

Dimension of Teachers Pedagogical Content Knowledge	Emphasis
Orientation in Teaching Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student-centered Learning
Knowledge of Curriculum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Spiral Progression of Science Curriculum • Critical Content in Science Teaching
Knowledge on Students' Understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How students learn Science
Knowledge on Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performance-based Assessment • Portfolio Assessment
Knowledge on Instructional Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi/interdisciplinary approach • Science technology-society approach • Contextual learning • Problem/issue-based learning • Inquiry-based approach.

Finally, with regards to the knowledge of instructional strategies, teachers used teacher-centered instructions which are lecture, discussion, and teacher demonstration. The reason the teachers might not be using student-centered instructions could be related with their orientations (Brown et al, 2013; and Sen, 2014) and their lack of knowledge of the different instructional approaches. It is therefore, recommended that teachers must be knowledgeable and use instructional strategies that are student-centered as concept mapping, everyday life

approaches and active learning (Sen, 2014). Besides, Science Curriculum (2013) suggested the use multi/interdisciplinary approach, science technology-society approach, contextual learning, problem/issue-based learning, and inquiry-based approach. These approaches are based on sound educational pedagogy namely, constructivism, social cognition learning model, learning style theory, and brain-based learning.

In the light of the findings of the study, it is also recommended for the Curriculum Implementation Division and the Office of Human Resource Development of the Schools Division of Bukidnon to design professional development program that would capacitate and enhance teachers' pedagogical content knowledge in teaching science. Matrix 1 shows the area and emphasis of teachers' professional development.

This also recommends for further studies. Firstly, it is recommended to study on more specific issues about PCK because PCK is a complex structure and explanation of the broad topics. Investigating teachers PCK through other data collection such as interview, observation, and document analysis is recommended. PCK in teaching science studies could focus on their relationship by use of qualitative, quantitative and mixed method in the future. Similarly, PCK studies could integrate learning and teaching, thus the following studies could be conducted with teachers PCK, student achievement and their relationships. Finally, teachers' PCK in teaching science can be replicated with science major teachers and out-of-field teachers in different levels (elementary and secondary) to have a comparative analysis of teachers' PCK.

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